

Dynamic Wireless Charging For Electric Vehicles

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Abstract—This paper demonstrates about the potential of dynamic charging system for an electric vehicle through wireless means. The cruising range of an Electric Vehicle (EV) can be augmented by a dynamic (wireless) charging system where the battery can be charged while the vehicle is on motion. But, the investment in infrastructure is huge and can be reduced by implementing the proposed system. In this concept, transmitter pads are incorporated into the road to demonstrate potential dynamic wireless charging system for an electric vehicle. Our major goal is to tackle the underlying problem of increasing power loss and to enhance the efficiency of the dynamic charging system. It has been proposed to use a switching circuit in coil system, so that can reduce the power loss by switching on the charging pads only when the vehicle arrives above them. There will be no power flow in the transmission coil, when there is no vehicle movement. This switching circuit will help in reducing the amount of energy that will be wasted by keeping all the transmitter coils energized all the time. Utilizing the switching approach also solves the problem of long charging time and limited driving range. This project demonstrated that power gadgets will be charged wirelessly via inductive coupling. To accomplish the same goal, simulation of 2 KW real time charging system for EV and hardware prototype of dynamic wireless power transfer was designed successfully using sequential logic.

Keywords—*Dynamic Wireless Power Transfer (DWPT), Sequential Logic*

I. INTRODUCTION

The potential for alternative technologies in automobiles such as electric vehicles is dependent on improved technology, distance, incentives, regulation, cost, and infrastructure. The dependency of fossil fuel and CO₂ emissions are considerably reduced by using Electric vehicles. The inconvenience due to plug-in charging methods and limited cruising range poses significant challenges to EVs technology. Additionally, others claim that EV technology is not viable for huge trucks and buses that need lengthy cruising ranges since batteries are typically expensive and heavy. But through the dynamic wireless power transfer system, heavy vehicles that need a lot of energy to run need not to have big batteries, and in future able to move even more people and objects.[1-5].

Recently, wireless power transmission permits automobiles to be charged under motion or on rest when parked. With this technology, users can forget about the nuisance of having to plug in charging cables and may cruise without thinking about running out of battery power. Dynamic Wireless Power Transfer (DWPT) can shorten charging and refueling times while also easing range anxiety. In DWPT, electromagnetic fields transferred from a transmitter implanted in the road to a receiver at the underside of the car are used to supply electricity to a moving vehicle. The wireless charging system for EVs through inductively coupled power transfer technology has been modeled and simulated in many literatures [6-15].

To transfer more charging power to the battery of the electrical car, we intend to employ multi-receiver coils in our model, which will be more effective than the conventional single-receiver coil since they will always be closer together than in a single coil system. In order to limit power loss by turning on the charging pads only when the vehicle passes over them. When the vehicle is not moving, there will be no power flow via the transmission coil. In this paper, a focus is on the development of models that can be used to support the design of DWPT systems. The simulation is carried out using MATLAB software.

The organization of this paper is as follows. Section II discusses the components of Dynamic Charging system. The simulation model of the wireless power transfer has been discussed in section III. Section IV explores dynamic wireless charging system using sequence logic technique. Section V discusses the hardware implementation

II. DYNAMIC WIRELESS POWER TRANSFER CHARGING

The dynamic charger is used to charge an Electric Vehicle while moving on an induction coil track. The charger is working on electromagnetic induction principle. It has a simpler structure of static wireless charger; both the charger has transmitter and receiver pad but the dynamic charger has multiplier transmitter coil pads integrated on the road. While comparatively with the static and dynamic, the static is efficient. In dynamic the coupling of coil is a short period so; the losses are high. The dynamic has a major factor of Electric vehicle driving range being extended vehicles can prolong their travel time without the requirement for large batteries or costly infrastructure and frequent charging on the road will allow car manufacturers to reduce the size of batteries, and thereby cut the cost of the vehicle while elongating the lifespan of batteries. Batteries will be healthier when they don't discharge deeply. The Figure 1 shows the basic diagram of a dynamic wireless charging system.

There is a series of transmitter coils integrated inside the asphalt and these transmitted coils are powered using the ac supply. This wireless charging works on the principle of mutual induction.

Figure.1 Dynamic Wireless Charging System

When two mutually coupled coils are in place, the magnetic field in one of the coils tends generate the voltage in the next coil. This property is called mutual inductance. Due to this phenomenon when the electrical vehicle comes directly over the primary coil which is present in the road the power is transferred to the secondary coil. This secondary coil is usually connected to the rectifier to convert the AC voltage to DC and then stored in the battery of the electrical vehicles. Figure 2. Illustrates the basic block diagram of the dynamic EV charging system. It consists of grid, rectifier, compensation network, transmitter coil, receiver coil, AC/DC converter and a battery bank with battery management system.

(i) Source

The first component is the grid, the AC power is first taken from the power supply and then it is passed through the AC rectifier

(ii) AC Rectifier

The AC Rectifier which converts the AC voltage into DC. This involves a device that only allows one-way flow of electric charge. As we have seen, this is exactly what a semiconductor diode does.

(iii) Compensation Network

In this part we will have a capacitor connected to the inductor in parallel. This set up is known as the LC tank. The LC tank acts as tuned circuit. When a medium vibrates at the highest amplitude resonant frequency occurs. The resonant frequency is given by the formula

$$\text{Resonant Frequency, } f_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{LC}} \quad (1)$$

If the power is transmitted in the resonant frequency the maximum power transfer occurs and the power loss during the wireless transmission will be very less compared to other frequencies.

Figure.2 Block Diagram of Dynamic Charging

(iv) Transmitter Coil

The power flowing in this transmitter coil is wirelessly transmitted to the receiver coil which is integrated at the bottom of the electric vehicle. EV charging relies on the principle of charging using the right-handed screw rule.

(v) Receiver Side of EV

There is another compensator network in the receiving side, this compensation network is an AC-DC rectifier which converts the incoming AC current to DC current because the battery only stores the DC current. There is also a high frequency inverter used in this model to convert the incoming DC voltage to AC voltage. The use of the High frequency inversion is to increase the frequency of the resulting AC voltage.

III. SIMULINK MODEL OF WIRELESS POWER TRANSFER

The simulation model of the wireless power transfer is done using MATLAB/SIMULINK software. From Figure 3, it can be seen that the WCS has two main sections, (i) Transmitter/primary coil and (ii) Receiver/secondary coil. The transmitter has a rectifier section and an inverter section but the receiver side keeps only a rectifier section. The transmitter is energized by the grid power and placed in the parking area of EV. The receiver is installed in the EV which is light in weight for convenience. Maximum power transfer from primary to secondary occurs when the system is operated in resonance frequency.

Capacitor C_p (primary side capacitor) and C_s (secondary side capacitor) are resonant capacitors. They are also used to compensate for the losses in the primary and secondary coil. Table 1 indicates the system parameters for the dynamic wireless charging system.

Table 1: System Parameters for Dynamic Wireless Charging

Parameters	Value
f_s	33 kHz
V_{in} (DC)	225 V
I_{in} (DC)	9.8
U_0	300 V
L_1	292 μ H
L_2	285 μ H
M	143 μ H
C_1	100 nF
C_2	100 nF
I_1	19 A
I_2	16 A
P_0	2039 W

Using these system parameters the simulation of the dynamic wireless charging using coil switching technique has been carried out.

Figure.3 Simulink Model of Wireless Power Transfer

Figure 3 shows the main system model of the dynamic wireless charging system using the coil switching technique. The input voltage of 325V obtained from AC source. The grid power is rectified and

inverted, before applying it to the primary coil. The output is also rectified and is connected to a lithium ion battery.

Figure.4 Rectifier Response

The Figure 4 shows the input response which is given to the HF inverter from the rectifier subsystem in the model. It shows the input voltage given to the rectifier from the grid is 271 volts, the output from the rectifier is 225 volts DC, input current 9.8 Amps and power 2 kW.

Figure.4 HF Inverter Subsystem

Figure.6 HF Inverter Output

The HF Inverter is used to increase the frequency range from standard 50 Hz to 30 kHz. It is achieved by a Pulse Width Modular (PWM). The Duty Cycle is set as 50% and given an input to PWM. In PWM,

the switching frequency is set as 33000 Hz. The output of the rectifier is connected to the LC tank and given to the HF inverter. The Figure 6 shows the output waveforms from the High Frequency inverter. It shows the AC output power of 1.5 kW, current of 6 Amps, voltage of 250 volts in waveforms respectively. This is then given to the primary transmitter coil.

The transmitter power is transferred wirelessly to the secondary receiver coil which is present in the electric vehicle and after passing through the rectifier. Figure 7 shows the output waveform of the battery during charging condition.

Figure.7 Battery Charging

It is evident from the battery output waveforms that the voltage is supplied across the battery wirelessly using coil switching technique. The SoC of the battery is increased effectively.

IV. DYNAMIC WIRELESS CHARGING USING SEQUENCE LOGIC

In the proposed worksequence logic technique for the coils in the transmitter side has been implemented. The coil switching technique is nothing but a switching technique in which different segments of coil will be switched as the Electric Vehicle passes by. In this technique the IR sensors were placed in between the coil segments. Usually, these coil segments consist about 10-15 set of coils. These IR coils are connected to ATmega controllers. As the electric vehicle passed above the IR sensor the sensor detects the movement of the electric vehicle and the input signal is given to the ATmega controller which is connected to the sensor.

Figure 8 illustrates the dynamic wireless charging system with the coil switching technique. It consists of three sets of transmitters each set consists of minimum of 10 transmitter coils. When an electrical vehicle containing receiver coils passes through an IR sensor, it sends the output signal to the ATmega controller.

After getting this signal as input from the IR sensor the controller knows that a vehicle is passing by a particular set of coils then it switch on that particular set of coils and after the vehicle completely passes that particular set of transmitter coils then the controller switches the next set of transmitter coils then it turns off it after the vehicle passes it and turn on the next set of transmitter coils it will keep on doing this

process until the end of the charging lane in which these transmitter coils are integrated for dynamic wireless charging.

Figure.8 Dynamic Wireless Charging System using Sequence Logic

V. HARDWARE IMPLEMENTATION

The block diagram shows the working of wireless charging of Electric vehicle whose basis is electromagnetic induction. The charging device will create an Electromagnetic field with alternating polarity using a coil of insulator copper wire & a similar coil will be placed inside the EV will converting Electromagnetic field back to electric current there by charging the battery.

When a transmitting coil emits electromagnetic waves matching the resonance frequency, there will be efficient transfer of energy to the receiving coil. The user is required to charge the battery after every 200 Km. The major aim of this project is to recharge battery wirelessly. This has been developed by converting a 230V, 50Hz AC supply into 12V 20 KHz .The output is sent to 20 KHz coil which is the primary of an air core transformer.

Figure.9 Electric Vehicle Wireless Charging system

(i) Transmitter Side Circuit

The 230V AC supply is being reduced into 12V DC using a 12V adapter. This adapter is used to supply precise 12V of DC current to a device. This 12V DC has to be converted into a high frequency

AC supply. The AC supply is boosted with the help of C₁, C₂, C₃ capacitors. The boosted supply is then given to an Astablemultivibrator. The desired frequency of 20 KHz for the AstableMultivibrator is controlled by the resistor R₆ and R₇ and C₄ capacitor which is connected to the AstableMultivibrator. The output pin 10 of the AstableMultivibrator is connected to the MOSFET. It acts as voltage-controlled current source, and is primarily used as switches for the amplification.

Figure.10 Transmitter Circuit Diagram

The D₂ Diode is used to conduct the electric current in only one direction. When the MOSFET is ON, positive signal is being sent to the coil. When MOSFET is OFF, negative supply is given to the coil. Arduino, microcontroller is used to store the code which helps in switching of coils. The IR sensor and relay is connected to the Arduino. The IR sensors are used to detect the vehicle. The IR sensors are embedded along the transmitter side to detect vehicle, thereby triggering the MOSFET to provide supply to the particular set of coil. Each IR sensor is connected to an individual relay. When an IR sensor sense, corresponding relay will be switched ON.

(ii)Receiving Side Circuit

The receiver circuit in the vehicle is shown in Figure 11.

Figure.11Receiving Circuit of Vehicle Side

The secondary coil absorbs the flux which is transmitted from the primary coil. The flux is converted into current which then passes through full wave rectifier convert. C₁ capacitor removes the noise from the full wave rectifier. D₁ LED used as indicator to receive the current from coil and R₁ resistor is used

to help the LED glow when the battery is charged parallel. D₂ diode connects in forward biased to prevent the discharging of the battery. Two gear motors are connecting parallel for veering the load capacity and capacitor C₂ used for removed the noise from the received by the motor.

(iii) Prototype Model using Sequence Logic

The output is fed to the primary of an air core transformer which has a 20 KHz tuned coil. The secondary coil develops 12V at 20KHz. The output of secondary is given to a high frequency bridge rectifier that delivers a constant charging current to super capacitor(100 F). In sequence logic technique the IR sensor were placed in between the coil segments.

Usually, the coil segments consists about 10 to 15 set of coils. These IR sensors and coils are connected parallel to the controller. As the electric vehicle passes above the IR sensor the sensor detects the movement of the EV and the input signal is given to the controller which is connected to the sensor. After getting the signal as input from the IR sensor the controller knows that a vehicle is passing by a particular set of coils then it switch on that particular set of coils and after the vehicle completely passes that particular set of transmitter coils then the controller switched the next set of transmitter coils then it turns off if after the vehicle passes it and turn on the next set of transmitter coils it will keep on doing this process until the end of the charging lane in which those transmitter coil are integrated for dynamic wireless charging.

(iv) Hardware Design of DWPT

Hardware model of the transmitter and the EV prototype is exhibited in the Figure 12. From the AC source, the voltage is stepped down using a 12V adapter. This adapter is used to supply precise 12V of DC current to a device. This 12V DC has to be converted into a high frequency AC supply. Eight relay module is used which acts as electrically powered switches. A relay's aim is to automate this power to turn electrical circuits on and off at certain periods. Both relay and coil are connected to the arduino. Arduino is given an external power supply of 5V.

Figure.12 Hardware Design of DWPT

The arduino is integrated to 8 IR sensors. Each IR sensor senses the motion of EV and triggers that particular coil. Once the EV moves on the transmitting track, the IR sensor senses the vehicle and triggers that particular coil. The energy is transferred to the EV and LED will indicate the battery charging.

VI. CONCLUSION

Dynamic wireless charging offers numerous advantages and opportunities for innovation in the field of wireless power transfer. This technology has high potential to revolutionize the charging devices by eliminating the need for cables and charging stations. The coil switching technique increases the power transfer in dynamic wireless charging of electric vehicles. When an electric vehicle approaches the charging lane each segment will be switched on and off based on the position of the electric vehicle. This is a strategy for efficiently turning on and turning off of the transmitter. A switching circuit has been placed for reducing the power loss. The Proposed system has been simulated in MATLAB/Simulink and the simulation output gives the output power of 2kW, voltage 388V and current 5.2A. The simulation of the arduino program for coil switching has also been implemented using the proteus software. The hardware prototype of dynamic wireless charging for electric vehicles was designed using a transmitter coil of 50 turns and a receiver coil of 300 turns. An output voltage of 2.2V in the receiving coil has been obtained.

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